

Complex Engineering Problem

Design and Exergy Evaluation of a Combined Cycle Power Plant Featuring an Organic Vapor Bottoming Cycle[†]

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Abstract: This research presents the design and exergy analysis of CCPP with gas cycle and ORC as bottoming cycle. The well structured approach is taken to design each component and its operating conditions. Hydrogen is selected as fuel for gas turbine and HFE 7000 is selected as working fluid of ORC. Major part of power is produced by Gas cycle and ORC utilizes waste heat to complement it. The exergy analysis of each individual component shows that major part of exergy destructions occurs in combustion chamber and HRSG.

Problem Statement: The work addresses the design and exergy analysis of combined power plant with gas cycle as topping cycle and organic Rankine cycle as the bottoming cycle with power output of 150 kW. The working fluid of ORC and the fuel for gas power cycle is to be selected based on minimum fuel utilization. It involves the selection of mass flow rates of fluids, design and power consumed by each component along with thermodynamical states. Further it requires the exergy analysis of the CCPP evaluating the exergy destroyed in each component and maximum exergy destruction and effect of increasing the boiler pressure is to be analyzed.

Cite this: DOI: 10.1039/d4nr01672f

Received 16th April 2025

Accepted 22th April 2025

Introduction

Energy is the fuel of modern economies, imparting an effect on every sector in the world. The efficient use of energy due to the scarcity of its resources and increased demand is of great importance. The combined power plant efficiently utilizes the energy as compared to a single power cycle, increasing its availability. The combined power plant offers higher efficiency by using multiple energy generation sources¹. Over the years, various studies have examined the performance and efficiency of the combined power plant. Involving different cycles as gas cycle, steam cycles or waste heat recovery cycle, to utilize en-

ergy.² performed the exergy analysis of a 747 MW CCPP in Pakistan. The analysis using EES was performed by³ in Egypt, analysing the effect of power output with the change in ambient temperature. The gas turbine is the most important component of the gas power cycle It relies on the specific fuels to achieve the optimal thermodynamic performance for power generation. Various fuels as natural gas, coal, syngas and hydrogen are analysed to be used in the cycle in accordance with practical and Environmental constraints⁴. Recent advancements show that hydrogen can be a potential leader against global warming due to its zero carbon emissions and sustainable development⁵.

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The study⁶ explains the burning of hydrogen in the gas turbine. The development and testing for low NOx Hydrogen combustion system is studied in⁷. The prospects and challenges in using it as a fuel are discussed in⁸, including the methods to reduce NOx emissions and safety requirements in the hydrogen gas turbines. The Organic Rankine cycle has proved as an efficient option for waste heat recovery, utilizing the low-grade energy to produce useful work. The working fluids used in the ORC are of great importance in terms of cycle efficiency, and power generation. The working fluids for the ORC are refrigerants with specific properties that are feasible for its application. The working fluids for the ORC are examined for better performance in⁹.

The HFCs used as working fluids possess a great impact on the global warming and ozone depletion due to their high GWP and ODP¹⁰. Hydrofluoroethers are less hazardous to the environment, having zero ODP and low GWP. In¹⁰ HFEs are examined based on various physical factors as the turbine size factor. The¹¹ conducted the study to analyze the exergy and economic perspective of selecting the fluid for ORC. The literature includes the analysis of higher power CCPP with effect of fuel used in the Brayton cycle and prospects and limitations in their usage. Additionally, the ORC employed as the bottoming cycle is also studied for effective waste heat recovery particularly with respect of working fluids used and their impact on the environment. This study focuses on the design and exergy analysis of small-scale CCPP with emphasis on fuel selection to minimize fuel utilization. It includes the detailed exergy destruction analysis for each component of cycle to identify improvements in design to increase efficiency. Additionally the choice of components and working fluid for the ORC is carefully considered to enhance the system performance. By implementing the design and exergy analysis for the small-scale CCPP, this study intends to provide the optimal operating conditions of the cycle for sustainable energy solutions.

Approaches and Methodology

Combined cycle power plant includes a gas turbine cycle and a vapor cycle to recover the heat rejected by the gas cycle. The thermal efficiency of CCPP is high as compared to a single gas cycle due to multiple work generation processes and waste heat utilization. The designed CCPP is small-scale with a power output of 150kW, with each component selected is in accordance with practical constraints. It can be used for applications like decentralized grids and rural electrification. This design intends to provide the optimize parameters for CCPP working conditions.

Modelling Assumptions

The following assumptions are made in the system to simplify the analysis of the system.

1. The system is considered to be in steady-state conditions, with no time-dependent variations.
2. The isentropic efficiency of the compressor and the turbine are assumed to be constant and equal to 0.85 and 0.87, respectively¹².
3. The isentropic efficiency of the ORC pump and the turbine are assumed to be constant and equal to 0.85 and 0.80, respectively⁹.
4. The working fluid is assumed to be treated as an ideal gas with variable specific heat.
5. The effectiveness coefficient of the air-gas heat exchanger is equal to 0.85¹².
6. The pressure drop in pipes and components is negligible.
7. Fuel is supposed to be hydrogen, and its temperature is equal to the ambient temperature.

Equations

The Following equations are used in the analysis

$$\oint_{\text{cycle}} \delta Q - \oint_{\text{cycle}} \delta W = 0$$

$$\delta Q - \delta W = h_2 - h_1 + g(z_2 - z_1) + \frac{v_2^2 - v_1^2}{2}$$

Working Fluid Selection

The working fluid of ORC is of great importance in terms of cycle working conditions and efficiency; however its selection depends on the conditions but also on its environmental affects¹³. Heat source affects the selection criteria of fluid for the ORC. The ORC working fluids are the refrigerants with properties that enable them to be used in waste heat recovery applications. The traditional HFCs used as the working fluid have high GWP and ODP due to the presence of the radicals¹¹. Hydrofluoroethers are a potential substitute for the traditional refrigerants due to their zero ODP and relatively smaller GWP¹⁰. As of today, none of the conventional refrigerants can be used in ORC as a major part of these refrigerants are phased out (CFCs) or being phasing down (HFCs) or will be phased down in the near future due to their high GWP and ODP¹⁴. The HFE7000 is selected as the working fluid among other fluids due to environmental factors and thermal stability among other HFEs. The HFE7000 performed best among the selected fuels in¹³ and in its case turbine size factor was most optimized¹⁰.

Compound	CAS	MW (g/mol)	BP (K)	T_c (K)	P_c (MPa)	ΔH_{vap} (kJ/kg)	Flammability Limits	GWP (AR6)
HFC-245fa	460-73-1	134.05	288.25	427.10	3.654	192.52	Non-flammable	962.0
HFE-143a	421-14-7	100.04	248.93	377.92	3.642	180.60	10.5–21.5% (dry air)	616.0
HFE-245mc	22410-44-2	150.05	278.78	406.82	2.886	152.64	10.5–13.5% (dry air)	747.0
HFE-245mf	1885-48-9	150.05	302.39	444.88	3.428	186.54	Non-flammable	878.0
HFE-356mmz	13171-18-1	182.07	322.43	459.61	2.699	172.13	5.25–15.0% (dry air)	8.1
HFE-7000	375-03-1	200.06	307.34	437.66	2.478	–	Non-flammable	576.0
HFE-7100	163702-07-6	250.06	332.65	458.00	2.220	138.95	Non-flammable	544.0
HFE-7200	163702-05-4	264.09	349.25	482.02	1.976	131.82	Non-flammable	34.3
HFE-7300	132182-92-4	350.08	375.40	497.00	1.454	133.46	Non-flammable	405.0
HFE-7500	297730-93-9	414.11	412.30	559.00	1.625	111.72	Non-flammable	13.0

Table 1: Thermophysical Properties of Refrigerant ¹⁵

Fuel Selection

The fuel for the gas cycle is selected based on the requirement of minimum fuel utilization. The Hydrogen is selected as the fuel for the gas cycle due to its low heating value LHV that ensures the minimum consumption of the fuel. The importance of hydrogen as a fuel is due to its zero carbon emissions and as a potential substitute for the traditional global warming-causing fuels⁵. Hydrogen has 2.6 times the energy per unit mass value as gasoline. From the combustion perspective, it has better properties than any hydrocarbon fuel in terms of ignitability, low ignition delay, and higher flammability¹⁶.

Global warming poses a serious threat to the environment, and a phased transition toward renewable energy sources is important to mitigate the harmful effects on future generations. The future opportunities and challenges in using hydrogen as fuel in gas turbines are studied in⁶. The problems associated with hydrogen combustion include the NOx emissions, Combustion instability, safety concerns, and the transport of the fuel. The methods of reduction of NOx emissions contain selective catalytic combustion SCC and transporting the hydrogen in the form of less explosive gases as the blue ammonia is being practiced. The methods to reduce the explosion incidents of hydrogen due to its high diffusion and spontaneous combustion are discussed in¹⁷ to mitigate the harmful effects.

Operating Conditions

The operating conditions for the designed CCPP are in accordance with practical power plants. The gas cycle is designed to meet the major power requirement, and ORC utilizes its waste heat to produce power. The optimized conditions of the power plant affect the exergetic and thermal efficiency by 4%. For the combined cycle power plant, the determined optimum design parameters for the plant exhibit a trade-off between thermodynamically and economically optimal designs¹⁸. For the gas cycle, the expansion and compression ratio of the turbine and compressor are selected based on practically available components for

the small-scale power generation.

The ORCs turbine and pump are designed in accordance with working conditions and for optimized waste heat recovery, the fluids also effects the working conditions of the ORC¹⁹. The maximum temperature cycle reaches to 1179°C. For the gas cycle the compression and expansion ratio is taken as 5, and for the ORC the pressure ratio is selected as 7.5. Due to increased complexity, the pressure drops in the cycle are considered to be negligible.

Figure 1: Combined Cycle Power Plant

Results and Discussions

This study intended to design CCGP and perform exergy analysis to find the exergy destruction and maximum exergy destroyed in each component with focus toward minimum fuel utilization and efficiency of the power plant. The gas cycle produced the 83.3% of the power requirement, and ORC produced the 17.7% of the needed. The mass flow rates of air and refrigerant are selected according to practical conditions, corresponding to optimized states. The expansion and compression in the turbines and compressors are affected by irreversibilities, leading to a decrease in efficiency. Back work ratio of the gas cycle is in the range of typical ratios for the gas turbine systems.

Parameter	Value
Air Mass Flow (\dot{m}_{air})	0.45 kg/s
Compressor Work Input, W_{comp}	90.93 kW
Gas Turbine Work Output, W_{turbine}	215.9 kW
Back Work Ratio, r_{bw}	42.1%
Net Work Output from Gas Cycle, $W_{\text{net, gas}}$	125 kW
Refrigerant Mass Flow ($\dot{m}_{\text{refrigerant}}$)	1 kg/s
ORC Compressor Work, $\dot{w}_{o, \text{comp}}$	0.6117 kW
ORC Turbine Work Output, $\dot{w}_{o, \text{turbine}}$	25.62 kW
Net ORC Work Output, w_{ORC}	25.01 kW
Total Net Power Output, W_{tot}	150 kW
Overall Thermal Efficiency, η_{total}	33.18%

Table 2: Summary of Power and Efficiency Results for Combined Cycle System

Exergy Analysis

Exergy is the available or useful form of energy. It quantifies the quality of energy as according to second law of thermodynamics higher quality energy can be converted completely into low quality energy but vice versa is not true. The exergy analysis is performed to calculate the waste work potential and to enhance the design of CCGP. Each component is analysed for the exergy destruction to improve design and efficiency of CCGP. Exergy analysis is divided into two components endogenous and exogeneous exergy destruction²⁰. The major part of exergy is destroyed in combustion chamber and HRSG²¹. The study²⁰ shows that thermal and exergy efficiencies increases significantly with increase in pressure compression ratio and turbine inlet temperature.²² shows that the adiabatic flame temperature of hydrogen is 2254° which is used to evaluate the exergy destruction in the combustion chamber.

Component	Exergy Destroyed (kW)
Gas Compressor, \dot{I}_{comp}	7.4
Gas Turbine, \dot{I}_{turbine}	0.65
Combustion Chamber, \dot{I}_{cc}	177.1
Heat Exchanger, \dot{I}_{HRSG}	93.26
ORC Turbine, $\dot{I}_{o, \text{turbine}}$	4.83
ORC Pump, $\dot{I}_{o, \text{pump}}$	0.09
ORC Condenser, $\dot{I}_{o, \text{condensor}}$	7.9

Table 3: Summary of Exergy Destruction Results for CCGP Components

The exergy analysis performed shows that combustion chamber, HRSG and condensor accounts for 92.1% of total exergy destruction. Among all components largest exergy destruction occurs in combustion chamber where hydrogen is burned as a fuel. Secondly HRSG between both cycles have second largest exergy destruction.

Effect of HRSG Pressure

The HRSG is crucial component in CCGP as the pressure of air and organic fluid is increased in the exchanger, so turbine exit temperature of gas cycle increases due to which net work output of gas cycle decreases but due to increased pressure of organic fluid in the exchanger the turbine inlet temperature increases so net work output of the ORC increases; however in our designed CCGP due to increased pressure in HRSG the net work output decreases.

Environmental Impact of CCGP

The impact of CCGP as compared to a single gas turbine on the environment is positive due to higher thermal efficiency and optimized utilization of waste heat than a single power cycle. It efficiently utilizes energy due to multiple work-producing components. The CO₂ emissions are reduced in the CCGP due to less fuel consumption, mitigating the harmful effects on environment. Our designed CCGP uses hydrogen as a fuel, so due to higher flame temperature, NO_x emissions increase, but utilizing selective catalytic combustion, it can be reduced to safe levels. The overall impact of CCGP on the environment is prospective, so well-designed and optimized CCGP can reduce the harmful impact on the environment than single gas cycle.

Conclusion

This study focuses on design and exergy analysis of CCGP with a gas cycle as a topping cycle and ORC as bottoming

cycle. The hydrogen is used as the fuel for the gas turbine due to its high LHV and zero carbon emissions. The expansion and pressure ratio of the both cycles are selected in accordance with practical working power plants. The heat exchanger acts as the heat source for ORC and sink for gas cycle, The HFE7000 is used as the working fluid in the ORC due to its enhanced thermal properties and environmental considerations. Exergy destruction analysis is performed in the study calculating the exergy destruction of each individual component. Analysis performed shows the HRSG and combustion chamber as the major source of exergy destruction. The study can be enhanced further by accounting for pressure drops in the cycle and dealing with the gas mixture instead of taking it as air. The combustion analysis can be enhanced by including each component of combustion in the analysis.

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